

HORIZON-EIC-2022-PATHFINDEROPEN-01**PERSEUS**

**2D Material-Based Multiple Oncotherapy
Against Metastatic Disease Using a
Radically New Computed Tomography
Approach**

DELIVERABLE

**WP5 – D5.3 – Dissemination and
Communication Plan**

ABSTRACT

This Dissemination and Communication Plan outlines PERSEUS project's strategies for widespread visibility and result dissemination. Target audiences include researchers, students, policy groups, and private-sector professionals. Central tools include the Project Website, social media, and participation in workshops. The plan also provides branding guidelines.

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Disclaimer

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Statement of originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation, or both.

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This Dissemination and Communication Plan specifies the dissemination strategy, activities, and materials that the PERSEUS consortium intends to use over the lifetime of the Project, with the overall goal of making it as visible as possible and of disseminating the Project's results as widely as possible, thus helping to maximise its impact.

The aim of communication is to address society at large by targeting the demographics therein that are relevant to PERSEUS. On the other hand, dissemination in PERSEUS has the three-fold goal of 1. increasing awareness & uptake of project results in the scientific community 2. fostering transfer of knowledge and new, further scientific collaborations 3. informing and attracting potential new funders, adopters, and collaborators for post-project development. Dissemination is designed to complement, support, and harmonise the activities of *WP6 (Work Package 6) Exploitation & Innovation Management*.

The dissemination and communication activities are thus targeted to reach:

- the scientific community, in particular including both researchers in translational medicine and medical practitioners
- science enthusiasts and people who want to know more about science
- audiences from projects similar to PERSEUS
- high-school students
- policy-group members
- private-enterprise scientists and managers
- potential funders.

The Dissemination and Communication Plan identifies the methods to be employed to reach each of these target groups, how to tune the messages accordingly, and the expected outcome of those activities.

Central to the identity and presence of PERSEUS is the Project Website, whose role is described in this document and whose design is discussed in more detail in *D5.1 Project Website*.

In addition, the current document describes how PERSEUS intends to capitalise on the potential of social media (SM) for informing and spreading awareness on the project, as well as engaging with a wider audience.

Finally, Workshops, Webinars, and Edit-A-Thons will also play an important role in the dissemination and engagement process, ensuring, together with the Website and SM profiles, that the results reach a broad range of pertinent audiences across Europe and beyond.

This document serves as an easy-to-use internal guide for the project partners. In addition, it describes the dissemination methodologies and activities to be carried out by partners in the project and how these processes will be monitored.

A further aim of this document is to streamline and standardise the procedures concerning the project's dissemination activities, and to provide PERSEUS partners with branding guidelines to be adopted. The standardisation of procedures will also help the project management in monitoring and reporting activities and outcomes.

We acknowledge that the present document is built on the successful dissemination experiences and strategies of previous European projects such as EAGLE, Q-SORT, MINEON, and SMART-electron.

2 STRUCTURE OF THE DOCUMENT

This document features 7 chapters.

Chapter 1 and 2 provide a brief overview of the deliverable's objectives and the structure of the document.

Chapter 3 describes the goals that PERSEUS intends to reach through its dissemination, communication, and engagement activities as described in the description of action (DoA).

Chapter 4 describes the target audience to be reached.

Chapter 5 analyses the variety of dissemination, communication, and engagement methods to be adopted with the overall goal of making the Project, its activities, and its outcomes more widely known.

Chapter 6 describes the criteria and the methods for evaluating the effectiveness of dissemination and communication activities.

Chapter 7 briefly summarises the conclusions.

3 WHY AND WHAT: GOALS

The aim of PERSEUS's outreach is to spread awareness of activities, results, and knowledge generated by the project. It will do so by broadcasting exciting, meaningful 'information nuggets' online through a variety of strategies, as well as by engaging citizens in participatory events (and/or their online version) pertaining to the world of science and science culture. In this effort, PERSEUS will also take advantage of the combined experience and capacity of its Consortium members.

PERSEUS aims to achieve the following objectives through its dissemination, communication, and public engagement activities:

1. To spread awareness and knowledge of the Project amongst other scientists and practitioners through dissemination, so as to foster future uptake of resulting PERSEUS-related techniques and technologies.
2. To foster through dissemination the enlargement of PERSEUS's scientific and enterprise network, for further future collaborations.
3. To spread awareness of the Project internationally amongst non-specialists through communication and engagement activities. This has the twin goals of spreading knowledge and awareness about science, as well as about EU-funded world-class research.
4. To promote science vocation among young people through communication and engagement.
5. To seek to meaningfully inform potential funders and collaborators for further development after the end of the project - for exploitation and/or continuation of research & validation activities.
6. To make European enterprises aware of the opportunities afforded by the European Commission (EC) Research & Innovation (R&I) projects.

Through this Dissemination and Communication Plan, WP5 intends to facilitate the achievement of the above-mentioned goals, including all the while the contributions of all PERSEUS partners and WP Leaders.

PERSEUS overall dissemination, communication and engagement ethos emphasises inclusiveness. This results in a fundamentally grassroots approach to science communication and in the involvement of civil society organisations such as the Wikimedia Foundation. The overall aim is to reverse the usually adopted strategies by embracing an inductive rather than a deductive approach to the communication of science. Therefore, the focus tends to be, rather than on 'science made understandable to people', on 'people made to participate in science initiatives'. Gender issues in science will be treated with particular attention.

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All dissemination and communication activities will be conducted under the coordination of the partner QED, which will ensure the delivery of a consistent message from the Project to the 'outer world'.

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4 WHO: THE PERSEUS TARGET AUDIENCE

The various target groups for PERSEUS were determined based on the overall goals of dissemination and communication. In decreasing order of overall expected reach, they are: the research community, science enthusiasts and the curious, audiences from PERSEUS 'sister' projects (i.e. projects that share similar subjects of domains of application with PERSEUS), high-school students, private-enterprise scientists and managers, and prospective funders. Within each of these demographics, special consideration will be given -within the constraints of PERSEUS's limited funding for outreach- to the so-called 'silent stakeholders', i.e., disadvantaged or minority categories such as women, the elderly, the poor.

The above target audiences are made up of either specialists (i.e. scientists) or non-specialists. Reaching specialists is important for the uptake of the science and technology developed in PERSEUS. Reaching non-specialists is important as a cultural mission in general, but also to spread awareness about cutting-edge research, its importance, and how adequately the EU is funding it.

4.1 The research community

This community is represented by researchers and experts working in the fields of nanoscience and solid-state physics, materials science, theranostics, nanomedicine, biochemistry, nanotoxicology, pharmacology, biomedical engineering and oncological translational studies. All these scientists can potentially benefit from the results of the project, either from the application of the project in their respective disciplines, or from the adoption or development of techniques/tools developed for PERSEUS. Besides the uptake of knowledge and techniques generated during PERSEUS, this demographic is essential for expanding the scope of possible future collaborations and strategic partnerships. We also consider national groups, European and International organisations to be part of this community.

- **National research-agency scientists**

A significant subset of the research community, this large and diverse group can be easily reached through specialised channels (*e.g.*, mailing lists) and may benefit from PERSEUS scientific results by reusing them at a national level - *e.g.* by adopting PERSEUS-related technologies and practices. Also, open data made available by PERSEUS might possibly find use as training datasets for the machine learning community.

4.2 Science enthusiasts and people who want to know more about science

Citizens who have an interest in science, from different countries and from a diverse range of socio-economic backgrounds, are our prime non-specialist target, as they are easier to reach -thanks to already-existing communities and groups of interest- and much more likely to appreciate PERSEUS's scientific aspects. It is important to reach this large group both as a cultural mission as well as to inform taxpayers on how public moneys are being invested.

Besides a variety of online posts and initiatives (see Section 5), events targeted to reach this demographic, such as the PERSEUS Science Bash events, will take place in new, unusual locations generally not taken into consideration for the public understanding of science; these might be pubs

(possibly as Pint of Science events), clubs, cafès; but also music and art festivals happening in the same city. The choice of these new locations aims to extend the reach of PERSEUS to those who are interested in science but generally do not frequent traditional venues. This also reflects our overall preoccupation with trying to reach the so-called ‘silent stakeholders’, i.e. under-represented portions of the public such as women, the elderly, the poorer, recent immigrants. Content-wise, references to local/regional conditions will be featured whenever possible, leveraging PERSEUS partners’ existing connections to local territories. Unfortunately, PERSEUS’s limited budget allows just for a handful of live events, but these will be highly targeted, and their success will serve as a metrics for future suchlike initiatives in EC projects. Regular mini-events for this demographic will also comprise Wikimedia Edit-a-thons.

4.3 Audiences from PERSEUS ‘sister’ projects

PERSEUS shares similar target audiences with other nanotechnology, theranostics, and translational medicine EC-funded projects. Also, other EIC projects share similar non-specialist target audiences with PERSEUS.

Outreach synergies with these projects hold the potential for a multiplier effect. Collaboration with sister projects is also important in order to optimise effort and avoid duplication of messages. The projects that could benefit from dissemination/engagement synergies with PERSEUS are listed in *Section 5.3 Dissemination, communication, and public engagement channels*.

4.4 High-school students

This demographic is important in general because it represents the citizens of tomorrow. It is also strategically important to reach in order to begin to address the vocational crisis in science subjects that is being felt in some EU countries. The low proportion of students and graduates in science and technology is, in fact, a concern for future innovation capacity in the EU. Putting high-school students in touch with the beauty and the challenges of cutting-edge research in science is one of PERSEUS’ aims. Providing informal science education by illustrating key concepts related to PERSEUS is another one. Since high-school students are highly active on social networks, these will be our primary conduit to reach them.

4.5 Policy-group members

This target group includes policy makers at the national and European levels.

At the European Level the target is mainly represented by the Member States and by the Directorate-General for Research and Innovation of the European Commission, which defines and implements European Research and Innovation (R&I) policy. Communication with this group is important in order to spread awareness of recent scientific developments as well as to propose best practices and improvements in how resources for R&I are invested.

Dissemination targeted to these users is important for the sustainability of the Project. Disseminating PERSEUS results among government ministries and agencies, which control or lobby for funding research institutions of all sorts, is valuable in order for PERSEUS partners to be supported in the future at the national government level. Communication towards this group is fundamental to ensure a more adequate level of national funding for research. This is of great importance in order to keep the research ecosystem alive.

4.6 Innovators from the private sector

This demographic is significant with view to possible strategic partnerships, especially for post-project developments, including the continuation of validation/trial activities. The scope of this demographic and the criteria with which to address it will be defined in consultation with the WP6 Leader, BeDimensional (BeD). This demographic will be addressed broadly at first, and then will be better defined by taking into account the outputs of *D6.2 Exploitation plan* and of *D6.3 Market assessment*. Companies in the European Economic Area (EEA) are especially relevant due to the possibility to include them in future EC projects and networks.

The other aim of targeting this group is so that interested parties become aware of the opportunities provided by the EIC Pathfinder programme for the private sector in the EU/EEA. Two enterprises, BeD (a technology company) and QED (a media production company) are already part of the PERSEUS consortium and can provide insights.

4.7 Potential funders

Making this group aware of PERSEUS' activities and results is important for exploitation, but also for seeking resources for the continuation of validation/trial activities after the end of the Project. The scope of this demographic and the criteria with which to address it will be defined in consultation with the WP6 Leader, BeDimensional. Like the previous demographic, this group will be defined broadly at first, then it will be better characterised based on the outputs of *D6.2 Exploitation plan* and of *D6.3 Market assessment*. This diverse group includes science-funding agencies, foundations, business angels/high net-worth individuals, venture capital companies, but also large pharmaceutical companies. Liaising with hospitals and foundations doing research on cancer will provide further leads. Think tanks can also serve as matchmakers between academics and science funding agencies¹.

4.8 Notes on the general public

The focus of PERSEUS dissemination and engagement is to increase awareness among selected stakeholders, so as to maximise the return on the investment made on these activities. However, insofar as possible given the limited resources allotted to WP5, we also want to try to address the wider public. Whilst it is generally considered futile to try to address a generalist audience without massive communication resources, we will nevertheless be taking a number of steps to ensure that our activities do not run the risk of alienating mass audiences. Therefore, as a general principle, we will:

- employ friendly, inclusive, and non-intimidating language
- seek to post high-quality, fresh content with far-reaching appeal
- include hashtags and channels that might help us reach new audiences
- when possible, strive to hold engagement events in new, non-intimidating locations such as pubs and cafès.

¹ <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-023-02602-9>

The latter will allow PERSEUS to reach new audiences that tend to avoid the more traditional spaces that are generally being used to communicate science.

4.9 General overview of target groups and corresponding messages

The following table summarises the type of audience, the messages to be communicated, the foreseen impact, and the partners' involvement.

AUDIENCE	MAIN MESSAGE TO BE COMMUNICATED ²	MAIN IMPACT	PERSEUS ACTORS INVOLVED
The research community	<p>New PERSEUS-related tools, techniques, knowledge are available or are being developed with potential applications <i>in your domain</i></p> <p>#CuttingEdgeResearch #CuttingEdgeResearchInTheEU #EUfundsResearch #nanoscience #pharmacology #2Dmaterials #Xrays #translationalstudies #theranostics #newtherapies #nanomedicine [other more specific hashtags will also be used]</p>	National, European, International	All partners, WP Leaders and EAB
National research-agency scientists	<p>New PERSEUS-related tools, techniques, knowledge are available or are being developed with potential applications <i>in your domain</i></p> <p>#CuttingEdgeResearch #CuttingEdgeResearchInTheEU #EUfundsResearch #nanoscience #2Dmaterials #Xrays #translationalstudies #theranostics #newtherapies [other more specific hashtags will also be used]</p>	National, European, International	All partners

² Hashtags are used here for the sake of conciseness. Some messages will change as the Project develops.

Science enthusiasts and people who want to know more about science	Science is beautiful Research is important The EU invests in research #SciencelsCool #CuttingEdgeResearch #CuttingEdgeResearchInTheEU #EUfundsResearch #FundResearchForAbetterWorld #MakingTheFutureHappenNow #ScienceAgainstCancer #cancerresearch	National, European, International	All partners under the guidance of QED
Audiences from PERSEUS 'sister' projects	#CuttingEdgeResearch #CuttingEdgeResearchInTheEU #EUfundsResearch #SciencelsCool #BecomeAscientist #MoreGirlsInSTEM #MakingTheFutureHappenNow	National, European, International	All partners, but mainly WP leaders
High-school students	#SciencelsCool #BecomeAscientist #MoreGirlsInSTEM #MakingTheFutureHappenNow	National, European	All partners
Policy groups, agencies and governments	Make more regular funding available for fundamental research at the national level Ask for increased R&I budget at EU level #MakingTheFutureHappenNow #MoreWomenGirlsInSTEM #FundResearchForAbetterWorld #CuttingEdgeResearchInTheEU #EUfundsResearch	National, European, International	All partners
Scientists and managers from the private sector	PERSEUS EC-funded consortium is developing and validating a new cancer treatment based on X-ray activated nanosystems #translationalstudies #newCancerTreatment #newXrayCancerTreatment #newNanosystemForCancerTreatment #newtherapies #theranostics #nanomedicine #nanoscience #pharmacology #2Dmaterials #Xrays EU funding is available for enterprises that want to do research	Mainly National & European, but also International	All partners under the guidance of BeD

	#EUhelpsEnterprises #EUFundsResearch #MakingTheFutureHappenNow		
Potential funders	PERSEUS EC-funded project is developing and validating a new cancer treatment based on X-ray activated nanosystems #translationalstudies #newCancerTreatment #newtherapies #theranostics #nanomedicine #nanoscience #2Dmaterials #Xrays	National, European, International	All partners under the guidance of BeD
General Public	#SciencelsCool #EUFundsResearch #BecomeAscientist #MoreGirlsInSTEM #MakingTheFutureHappenNow	National, European, International	All partners under the guidance of QED

4.10 Cross-cutting target groups: common tags and hashtags

Some hashtags and tags cut across all the above demographics. These are chosen in order to reach out to established audiences pertaining to other existing social media entities or to new or existing audiences clustering around certain topics. Our rule of thumb for tagging is to include:

- all PERSEUS partners and partners of each specific initiative;
- institutions, and companies in their extended network;
- any active channels from the EU on the chosen medium/media;
- personal profiles in the case of involved or influential individuals.

These common tags and hashtags are based on either main brand / concept fostering, e.g.:
#PERSEUS #EUFunded #EICpathfinder #EIC #FET #sciencebash #pintofscience #EU
#EuropeanResearch

Or on shared institutions / sister projects / brands, e.g.:

@EU_Commission @Wikimedia @ERC_Research @CERN @OpenAIRE_eu #EICFTW
@EUScienceInnov @StampaCnr @Wikimedialitalia #FutureTechWeek

Or on shared themes, e.g.:

#STEM #openlabs #education
#science #technology #innovation #research
#nanotechnology #nanoscience #oncology
#fightcancer #cancerresearch #theranostics
#womeninscience @WomenScienceDay @WomenInOptics @4womeninscience
#sciencewelike #sciencecomm #scicomm

#sneakpreview
#design #beauty #beautifulscience
#totebag

Or on relevant scientists' / politicians' / SMM profiles.

This type of tagging is especially useful for LinkedIn posts, in order to reach scientists or science managers who might be interested in PERSEUS research or technologies.

Or on relevant groups of interest, e.g.:

EU Science & Innovation, Research and Executive Agency, European Innovation Council.

On X (former Twitter), popular or trending hashtags related to the intended post at the moment of posting will also be used. These include hashtags pertaining to specific newsworthy events and hashtags on relevant themes.

5 HOW: METHODOLOGY

WP5 makes use of a variety of dissemination and public engagement methods.

As a general remark, given the limited budget that EC projects are able to allot to dissemination and communication efforts, promotion of PERSEUS through traditional mass media is not economically viable, in the sense that advertising is too expensive for adequately promoting PERSEUS. On the other hand, online communication, especially through social media, is more affordable and can be tailored with great precision to specific groups - defined by a combination of interests, age range, geographic location. It therefore provides a truly optimal return on investment, which is why it will be used extensively for PERSEUS.

Messages will vary through the lifetime of the Project. In the initial phases, dissemination is more focused on encouraging awareness of the project, while with the evolution of the Project it will increasingly focus on promoting its major achievements.

PERSEUS aims to expand the capacity of European and national science actors to effect better societal engagement. PERSEUS also aims to support a shift towards a more dynamic relationship between science and society. The project aims to achieve this objective by using and exploring recent cutting-edge innovation practices in public engagement (see Events in Section 5.3) within this composite and multifaceted field.

Inclusive, participatory events such as the Wiki Edit-a-thon, as well as the special attention paid to gender issues and minority stakeholders, also make PERSEUS compliant with RRI (Responsible Research and Innovation) policies. PERSEUS fully shares the RRI aim of engaging society in open science and innovation.

Finally, compliance with Open Science and Open Innovation EC policies is ensured by the project specific *D1.2 Data Management Plan*.

The following paragraphs briefly summarise our approach.

5.1 PERSEUS Branding Guidelines

When we say the ‘branding guidelines’ of the project, we mean a set of elements and instructions that should characterise the institutional communication of the project in order to simplify and make recognisable our communication activities (project visual identity, in short, see also *D5.2 Project Logo*).

Given the strongly interdisciplinary nature of PERSEUS and its potential for a significant societal impact, we feel it is equally important to pay attention to communicating to both specialised audiences and external, non-specialised audiences. In particular, the development of the following elements has been considered for PERSEUS's branding efforts:

1. Basic elements (see also: *D5.2 Project Logo*)

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- Brand Logo

PERSEUS Logo

- Branding architecture, meaning a cohesive system of typographical rules, visual relations and hierarchies between the brand-logo and the (typo)graphical elements connectable to it (e.g. the PERSEUS brand-logotype and event titles)

2. Web (see also: *D5.1 Project Website*)

Templates for the web pages [that are compatible with the CMS (content management system) of the portal], in particular:

- main portal page;
- general page template;
- events pages template, news template, partners' page template;
- contacts page template / Who We Are, etc.

The PERSEUS website is conceived for both desktop and mobile use

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PERSEUS home page

3. Graphic & printed materials (see also: *D5.4 Graphic assets*)

- Three-sided A4 foldable Project brochure design;
- PERSEUS branded tote bag design;
- 3x A2 Project Workshop poster designs;
- 1x Project vinyl banner design;
- A4 PERSEUS folder design;
- Favicons and banners for Social Media profiles.

These assets will be printed in the quantities that QED deems sufficient for the achievement of the dissemination and communication goals.

4. Ready-to-use layouts

- PowerPoint/Keynote template for presentations;
- A4 template for PERSEUS-headed paper for invitations and courteous communications
- Electronic communication documents (e.g. outreach toolkits).

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5.2 Adjusting the language according to the target audience

The PERSEUS project aims to develop knowledge and tools that can be technically complex and challenging. The language we use to communicate these ideas is therefore critical. Its importance cannot be underestimated, for it can make the difference between engaging or not engaging the target audience. Therefore, the same message content, when targeted at different audiences, often needs to be expressed in different ways: the language used must become more or less technical according to the intended audience it is addressing - to its model reader. For example, writing a paper for a scientific journal demands a more technical language, facilitating the reading with images, schemas, and tables. On the other hand, a short paper for the institution's newsletter or website needs to be expressed in non-technical terms using language that the audience is familiar with. Writing for the Web in general needs to present ideas clearly, and concisely. Also, crucially, there is a need to communicate complex concepts to other scientists from different fields (e.g. communicating physics to biologists). This is an intermediate, inter-disciplinary level of communication, which can make use of scientific concepts and terminology that are common to all foundation courses at university.

Therefore, PERSEUS can be said to have three distinct levels of communication: highly specialistic, interdisciplinary, and general public.

Specialistic communication is taken care of by the peer-reviewed articles that the Project begets, whose manuscripts are also Project Deliverables.

On the other hand, dedicated Wikipedia articles (see 5.3 below) were conceived as tools for the communication of information at all three different levels. Wikipedia articles can function as an interactive online lexicon that is particularly flexible and user-friendly, and which moreover is available to anyone. This is why we decided to invest time and resources in the **Wiki Edit-a-thons**.

5.3 Dissemination, communication, and public engagement channels

In this section we summarise the main conduits through which the Project will reach its intended target groups.

5.3.1 PERSEUS Project Website

The PERSEUS website has already been described in *D5.1 Project Website*, which illustrates its aims, the users that it targets, the adopted CMS, the implementation work, services, editorial board, and the tools for monitoring.

The PERSEUS website is the first point of contact for third parties interested in the project and its activities and it is the centre of the dissemination and communication strategy of PERSEUS. It facilitates the management of the **community** created around the project activities. The members of the community will be strongly encouraged to participate, as most of the communication will occur online.

The Website presents the project to all target audiences and gives detailed, tailored information to stakeholders and journalists on project progress, activities, and results (among other things). The aim is to publish news, data, and other relevant project deliverables in a way that can be useful to other researchers and potential business partners.

The website also features:

- a dedicated **News section** for the public at large, in which project activities are presented in a non-technical way; this section also includes photos and may include short mobile videos taken by project scientists, documenting what is going on;
- attached social media groups (Facebook, LinkedIn, X / Twitter);
- Web pages devoted to **layperson's explanations and introductions to basic physics concepts** at the heart of the project;
- a Web page devoted to the **scientific publications** produced by PERSEUS.

PERSEUS

People ▾ EU Funded News Gallery Press Contacts Search...

News

Project Perseus Unveils Visual Identity
April 28, 2023

Dr. Emma Lazzeri sheds light on Open Science obligations in Horizon Europe at the Perseus Project Kick-off
March 28, 2023

Checks off for PERSEUS!
March 16, 2023

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PERSEUS - News page

Users visiting the Website are thus able to:

- ★ browse Project News
- ★ download public files such as the latest Press Release and Outreach Toolkit, as well as published articles and public deliverables
- ★ replay the Interdisciplinary Webinars
- ★ access further reading about the science behind the project (Meet Your Scientist, links to online resources, etc.)
- ★ ask questions to PERSEUS scientists
- ★ browse PERSEUS past and upcoming Events
- ★ browse interesting and/or beautiful images

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5.3.2 Partners' websites

Partners are encouraged to disseminate PERSEUS activities and outcomes on their own institutional websites, periodically updating news, and links to relevant documentation. Partners have been asked to put links to the PERSEUS Website on their institutional websites, so as to increase its Google PageRank. More generally, the existing communication structure of the project partners will be engaged - see 5.3.4 *Partners' involvement*. Links to PERSEUS will be featured in news posts designed to draw attention to the project via short texts and attractive visuals, providing further reading where possible (e.g. media, news items, or deliverables on the project website).

5.3.3 Social networks

Dedicated SN profiles are a fundamental part of the Project's identity. In fact, a lively SN presence allows us to gradually build a community of interested users around PERSEUS. This is the most effective way to ensure visibility for the Project, which moreover benefits from the funnelling of users from the social network pages to its Website. Crucially, social network activity can be planned more easily than other forms of promotion thanks to the availability of relevant metrics. Thus, social networks help spread online word-of-mouth about the research progress and the wealth of Project materials made available on the Website.

Based on our target demographics, we activated PERSEUS profiles on the main social networks. We recently re-assessed SN presence and activities based on metrics from past EC projects, which confirmed the importance of LinkedIn as a platform for reaching through to scientists. Here are the corresponding links:

[Facebook](#)

[X \(former Twitter\)](#)

- *Content for social networks*

Social networks are an essential tool for communicating the project and building a community of interested users around it.

Highly engaging content -in the form of science news, interesting and/or beautiful images, pregnant/insightful quotes, scientists' snapshots or short mobile video testimonials taken during their work, etc.- will be regularly posted and promoted. Relevant existing communities, groups, and pages will be exploited to this end. A-B testing of posts is employed systematically, taking advantage of the metrics provided by platforms.

It is important to realise that SNs are media channels in their own right and, as such, need a clear editorial guideline and regular updates backed by a publishing plan drafted at regular intervals. To this end, social network posts for PERSEUS are created so as to conform to either one of the following categories:

- 1) General science posts

General-interest, inspiring science posts, pertaining to the physical and biochemical sciences. These can also be re-posts of existing excellent articles, with which PERSEUS shares the same target audience.

2) PERSEUS news and EC news

These are PERSEUS news proper: papers published, prizes, events, etc. EC news on R&I are part of this category.

3) Testimonials from researchers

These are images or interviews related to PERSEUS, chronicling work through personal perspective/updates, and thus bringing out the ‘human element’ behind scientific research.

4) Basic science terms explained

These are short posts on basic PERSEUS science concepts, explained by specialists: didactic but easy posts on basic subjects.

5) Brilliant images

Large, beautiful images pertaining to the project, with a short caption explaining their content. Eye-catching imagery is a prime conduit for engagement. Images providing insights into the science, technology, and concepts behind the project will be preferentially chosen.

5.3.4 Partners’ involvement

Partners are encouraged to promote PERSEUS activities and outcomes on their institutional mailing lists, newsletters/e-bulletins, and social media channels.

PERSEUS Partners regularly attend relevant scientific conferences, disseminating project brochures.

Greater Partner involvement in outreach in general will be sought by:

- establishing a common repository in which partners can upload images to be used for outreach, especially for social networks;
- establishing a regular conf call between all Partners devoted to discussing new outreach opportunities and ideas;
- providing training to Partners for taking better pictures, so as to enable them to provide significant snapshots of various aspects of lab life
- liaising with their relevant personnel (press office, communication managers, etc.).

5.3.5 Synergies with Wikimedia

Wiki Edit-a-thons will be organised with the aim of editing and improving Wikipedia entries on PERSEUS-specific topics. This approach allows PERSEUS to tap into the large user base of

Wikipedia. The importance of the synergy with Wikipedia, with its >125 million daily readers³, cannot be underestimated.

Selected PERSEUS images will also be published in Wikimedia Commons thanks to the support of [Wikimedia Italia](#); this will also give Wikipedia users the possibility to directly access (and reference in articles) a plethora of significant scientific sources.

5.3.5 Synergies with other PERSEUS ‘sister’ projects

PERSEUS will liaise with other EIC-funded sister projects to ensure full and effective collaboration. It will also seek to establish relationships with international projects in the same fields and the related flagship initiatives of the European Commission, such as for instance those of the Beating Cancer Plan.

For all these EC projects, QED will follow best practices developed in the past, based on mutual collaboration and the pursuit of ad-hoc agreements with PERSEUS, for supporting each other’s dissemination and communication efforts, e.g. by cross-posting.

5.3.6 Synergies with Open Access projects

The main ongoing projects facilitating and advancing Open Access belong to the OpenAIRE infrastructure. Since its inception, PERSEUS has been in close collaboration with the European Science Cloud Community. During the Kick-off Meeting for the Perseus Project at CNR-IMEM in Parma, Dr. Emma Lazzeri from GARR delivered a comprehensive Training Webinar on the significance and repercussions of Open Science within Horizon Europe. Furthermore, PERSEUS is committed to ensuring that Open Access is not only pivotal for the advancement of science but also for attracting emerging talents to Europe and it is devoted to help disseminate high-quality research knowledge to those who might not typically have access, thus fostering scientific literacy in otherwise underserved communities.

5.3.7 External events

Other important channels for the dissemination of project results include national networks, European and International workshops, seminars, and conferences organised by other institutions, as well as national and international fairs and exhibitions.

Individual PERSEUS members regularly attend relevant conferences and sister-project events and will disseminate project brochures. If possible, project brochures will also be occasionally sent for deployment to event organisers.

PERSEUS personnel also participate in relevant communication and/or networking events organised by the European Commission, such as the European Innovation Council Future Tech Week and the European Researchers’ Night.

³ Source: [https://stats.wikimedia.org/#!/all-wikipedia-projects/reading/unique-devices/normal|line|2-year|\(access-site\)~mobile-site*desktop-site|daily](https://stats.wikimedia.org/#!/all-wikipedia-projects/reading/unique-devices/normal|line|2-year|(access-site)~mobile-site*desktop-site|daily)

5.3.8 Scientific papers

All scientific partners publish in international journals, as well as in the proceedings of conferences in which they are invited. To this end, many PERSEUS deliverables have been conceived as manuscripts for research papers, to optimise the time and effort spent doing research. All research papers generated by PERSEUS bear the official acknowledgement of EC funding, specifying the Grant Agreement number.

5.3.9 PERSEUS publications and News

To disseminate the accomplishments of the various WPs to a broader audience, PERSEUS will circulate news regarding the project, its results, and publications on its website. Additionally, information will be shared through the EC channels, sister projects, and sent to pertaining mailing lists. Updates will also be posted on the chosen social media platforms.

5.3.10 PERSEUS Events

These are central to the dissemination and engagement effort. They consist of:

- a. 3 dedicated PERSEUS International Events, scheduled to work in synergy with major conferences held by sister projects and to dovetail with major related conferences;
- b. 3 Wikipedia Edit-a-thons
- c. related deployment of specific promotional materials:
 - i. Conference posters;
 - ii. Project brochures.

List of PERSEUS Events

Event	Date	Expected Audience	Location	Status
Kick-off Meeting	M1	All partners, European Commission, Civil Society Organisation (E.g. Wikimedia)	Real and virtual	Done
PERSEUS First International Workshop	M12-M24	All Partners, Sister Projects, Research Community	Real	To be organised
PERSEUS Second International	M24-M36	All Partners, Sister Projects,	Real	To be

Workshop		Research Community		organised
PERSEUS Third International Workshop	M36-M48	All Partners, Sister Projects, Research Community	Real	To be organised
PERSEUS Science Bashes	M18-M24 / M24-M36 / M36-M48	General Public / Silent Stakeholders / High School Students	Same ones as those of the International Workshops, if possible	To be organised
PERSEUS Wiki Edit-a-Thons	M18-M24 / M24-M36 / M36-M48	All Partners, Sister Projects, Research Community General Public / Silent Stakeholders / High School Students	Same ones as those of the International Workshops, if possible	To be organised

5.3.11 PERSEUS Teaser Video

The teaser video and its associated QED Vimeo channel are geared towards maximising the impact and visibility of PERSEUS. The Web-tailored teaser video is being produced in two versions of different length. It will feature fascinating insights into the physics and biology behind PERSEUS' treatment. Its visual language will be fresh and dynamic, seamlessly merging live action with CGI. The video is conceived for a general audience – however, science lovers, high-school students, and film buffs will especially appreciate it. The commercials will be mastered in HD (high definition); this will be done chiefly in preparation for their Web delivery, but will also afford them the possibility of being integrated into theatrical and broadcast exhibitions if so wished. All the intellectual property rights associated with the promo will be cleared so as to allow for its free distribution; more precisely, the makers will grant a non-exclusive licence to the PERSEUS Consortium, so that the video can be distributed as widely as possible via embedding and - if possible- broadcast and theatrical exhibition. A dedicated Vimeo link will be used for all embedding; crucially, this will also provide a set of useful metrics to measure the video's impact (number of embeds, number of total and partial plays, geographical spread of users, etc.).

5.3.12 SUMMARY OF CHANNELS/ACTIONS

The following table sums up the methods used by PERSEUS to disseminate its activities and outcomes.

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METHOD	PURPOSE	DESCRIPTION	REFERENCES	GUIDELINES FOR PARTNERS
Project website	<i>To:</i> <i>Raise awareness</i> <i>Disseminate</i> <i>Communicate</i>	The Project Website is one of the most versatile dissemination tools. It should ‘speak’ to different audiences, using the appropriate linguistic tools.	See <i>D5.1 Project Website</i> . This deliverable describes the website developed for the project, in particular the goals it intends to achieve, the users towards whom it is targeted, the software used, the implementation work, the services, the editorial board, the tools for monitoring the website.	Partners are encouraged to send relevant information, news, images to enrich the Project Website and be shared by all.
Partners’ institutional websites	<i>To:</i> <i>Raise awareness</i> <i>Engage</i> <i>Communicate</i>	Pages or dedicated pages on these websites are important for the dissemination of the project’s results at a national level and to direct traffic towards the Project Website		Partners are encouraged to publish a page or section describing the project’s activities and results on their institutional websites.
Social networks groups & mailing-lists	<i>To:</i> <i>Raise awareness</i> <i>Engage</i> <i>Communicate</i>	All these tools present an opportunity to be proactive and reactive, to share one’s knowledge with the target community, to further characterise and spread PERSEUS’ brand image , and to help spread online word-of-mouth about the progress of research.		Partners are encouraged to follow PERSEUS Social Network profiles. Partners who manage a professional blog or who are active on social networks are encouraged to promote and disseminate the Project and its results to their own audiences.

				Partners are encouraged to announce their achievements, publications, etc.
Wikimedia	<i>To:</i> <i>Disseminate</i> <i>Engage</i> <i>Communicate</i>	Opening up Wikimedia to experts interested in the topics of PERSEUS.		Partners are encouraged to edit Wikipedia entries and enrich the Wikimedia Commons with images produced during the project.
Press Releases and Newsletters	<i>To:</i> <i>Raise awareness</i> <i>Communicate</i>	A press release is a formal announcement to the national press. Partners are encouraged to issue press releases to announce any event or important PERSEUS achievement.	.	Partners should liaise with the Coordinator before issuing a press release and to include the PERSEUS logo, e-mail, and link to the website.
Brochures and other promotional material	<i>To:</i> <i>Raise awareness</i> <i>Communicate</i>	Although communication channels are often electronic, we believe that it is still useful to circulate printed dissemination materials at meetings and events.	The following materials will be available: <ul style="list-style-type: none">● PERSEUS Brochure● PERSEUS Poster Dissemination material may be downloaded from a dedicated page in the Project Website. A detailed description of PERSEUS Dissemination material will be provided in the related deliverable	Partners should disseminate PERSEUS promotional material at their professional events. All promotional material will be available for customisation and translation into other languages.

			D5.4. This document will be structured as an easy-to-use internal guide describing dissemination materials that have been completed or will be available in the near future, as well as guidelines on how, where, and when to distribute them.	
Sister projects and cluster meetings organised by the European Commission	<i>To:</i> <i>Raise awareness</i> <i>Engage</i> <i>Communicate</i>	Sister projects and cluster meetings are excellent opportunities for projects to learn from each other, discuss common issues, and receive feedback on their work. Partners may be asked to give a presentation, participate in a workshop, give a demo, etc. As there may be many projects on the agenda, we encourage partners to make an impact and engage the audience.	Events archive on PERSEUS website. Messages circulating in dedicated TEAMS mailing list.	Partners are advised to use the Project Website and internal mailing lists to inform the Consortium about professional meetings. Some of PERSEUS's experts could be interested in participating in one of them. Partners are required to always include the Logo when presenting or speaking about PERSEUS.
Conference presentations	<i>To:</i> <i>Raise awareness</i> <i>Engage</i> <i>Communicate</i>	National and international conferences are an excellent opportunity to share the PERSEUS Consortium's achievements with experts in the field (teaching/ learning, etc).	Events archive on PERSEUS website.	Partners are advised to strive to select conferences where their presentation will have an impact, and will attract the experts to whom they want to speak. Partners are directed

				<p>to always use the Logo when presenting or speaking about PERSEUS.</p> <p>Partners are encouraged to disseminate PERSEUS promotional material.</p>
Conference posters	<p><i>To:</i></p> <p><i>Raise awareness</i></p>	<p>A poster session at a conference may be more appropriate when there is work in progress. Posters may be presented to delegates who attend the session. It may not be as engaging as doing a presentation in the auditorium, but it is an excellent way to attract people and get one-on-one feedback. Often conferences do not foresee calls for papers, but do foresee poster sessions.</p>		<p>Partners are advised to strive to select conferences where their presentation will have an impact, and will attract the experts to whom they want to speak.</p> <p>Partners are advised to always include the PERSEUS Logo.</p> <p>Partners are encouraged to disseminate PERSEUS promotional material.</p>
PERSEUS Science Bashes	<p><i>To:</i></p> <p><i>Engage</i></p> <p><i>Communicate</i></p>	<p>Science Bashes are events that take place in casual settings such as schools, pubs, and cafès. They are open to everyone, and feature an engaging presentation/conversation with a scientist about a particular topic. Science Bashes are a grassroots</p>		<p>Partners should provide topics for the Science Bashes and engage the local communities in these events.</p> <p>Partners will be advised to disseminate PERSEUS promotional material on these occasions.</p>

		<p>initiative. Like science cafès, they exist all over the world and the format can vary from place to place. Venues range from local libraries, to school and coffee houses to neighbourhood bars. Even the names of Science Bashes vary, including Science on Tap, Science Pub, Ask a Scientist, and Café Sci.</p>		
<p>Wikipedia Edit-a-thons</p>	<p><i>To:</i> <i>Engage</i> <i>Communicate</i></p>	<p>An edit-a-thon is</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. a scheduled time where people edit Wikipedia together, whether offline, online, or a mix of both; 2. typically focused on a specific topic, such as science or women's history; 3. a way to recruit new Wikipedians and teach them how to contribute. Edit-a-thons improve the encyclopaedia and can be a great way to help new Wikipedians learn to edit. This is quite different from large conferences such as Wikimania, which often have multiple speakers or panels about a huge variety of topics. An edit-a-thon is also unlike a regular meetup, 		<p>Partners should provide topics for the edit-a-thons, engage the local communities in these events and to get in touch with the respective national chapter of Wikimedia.</p>

		<p>which tends to be without a single goal and/or for socialising. In other words, an edit-a-thon is like a hackathon for Wikipedians.</p>		
<p>Journal articles and/or publications</p>	<p><i>To:</i></p> <p><i>Raise awareness</i></p> <p><i>Disseminate</i></p>	<p>Partners are encouraged at every opportunity to author papers on the PERSEUS research.</p> <p>During the project, partners may wish to contribute to electronic newsletters, blogs, portals.</p> <p>Peer-reviewed journals in relevant disciplines will be a very important opportunity once we will have reached an advanced phase of the project, when there are data and results to report.</p>		<p>Partners are reminded to include in their work the compulsory acknowledgement of EC and UKRI funding, as well as recommended to reference the PERSEUS project.</p> <p>Partners must inform and send a copy of any journal article or academic paper to the Project Coordinator so that it may be published or mentioned on the PERSEUS website.</p>
<p>ZENODO</p>	<p><i>To:</i></p> <p><i>Raise awareness</i></p> <p><i>Disseminate</i></p> <p><i>Share data</i></p>	<p>Zenodo is a general-purpose open-access repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN. It allows researchers to upload and store data sets, research software, reports, and any other research-related file. PERSEUS opened its</p>		<p>Partners must inform and send a copy of any journal article or academic paper or deliverable to the project's coordinator so that it may be uploaded to the ZENODO repository.</p>

		own <i>community</i> on Zenodo, under which it collects the most relevant project data.		
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6 MONITORING AND SUCCESS INDICATORS

The following table lists the updated **key performance indicators** regarding the Project's dissemination, communication, and public engagement efforts.

Indicator No.	Objective/expected result	Indicator name	Expected progress		
			M12	M30	M48
1	Communication and engagement success	Total number of followers on social networks	500	1000	1500
2	Communication and engagement success	Maximum post reach on social networks	1000	2000	5000
3	Communication success	Number of countries reached through social networks and website	8	16	28
4	Communication, dissemination, and engagement success	Number of visitors on Project Website (unique IPs)	150	500	750
5	Communication and dissemination success	Total number of brochures/flyers distributed	1000	4000	7000
6	Dissemination success	Number of workshops/conferences attended by PERSEUS scientists	12	30	42
7	Dissemination success	Number of papers published	3	5	11
8	Dissemination success	Number of Project Events organised by PERSEUS	1	2	4
9	Dissemination and engagement success	Number of participants in the events organised by the PERSEUS	60	120	200
10	Communication and dissemination success	Number of visits to the PERSEUS Website	500	2000	5000
11	Dissemination success	Number of citations of PERSEUS papers	4	14	28
12	Engagement and communication success	Number of quotations or links or embeds of the	30	100	200

		PERSEUS project (Web, including social networks)			
13	Engagement success	Number of Wiki Edit-a-thons	0	2	3
14	Engagement success	Number of Science Bashes	1	2	3
15	Engagement success	Number of 'share' actions on Social Networks	100	200	300
16	Engagement success	Number of items (articles or media) enriched in Wikipedia and Wikimedia Commons	0	20	30

The effectiveness of dissemination, communication, and engagement activities is evaluated constantly with the following criteria:

1) Statistical analysis of the Project Website with the following indicators, in order to follow up on users' interest through Website content:

- Page views: number of webpages requested and viewed;
- Visits or sessions: number of visits to the site made by users;
- Unique visitors: number of individual users that have visited the site;
- Time spent: time spent in minutes and seconds while navigating or viewing the pages of a site or using a digital application.

[Google Analytics](#) is the main tool to collect fresh insights into how visitors use our site, how they arrived at our site, which parts of our website are performing well, which pages are most popular and how visitors interact with sharing features on the site.

In addition, the PERSEUS social network profiles are managed through [Hootsuite](#), a social media management tool that allows the PERSEUS dissemination and communication team to efficiently track conversations and measure campaign results.

7 CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable describes the initial Dissemination and Communication Plan for the PERSEUS project. The overall scope of the dissemination activities within the PERSEUS project is to ensure the maximal impact of the project by efficiently communicating project innovations to relevant target groups.

In particular, the Dissemination and Communication Plan aims to ensure that:

- the Project overall outreach activities follow the planned schedule and meet with success;
- the messages delivered from the Project to the 'outer world' are coherent and of a high standard;
- the Project maintains a high profile;
- the Project community at large learns from its achievements;
- the Project outreach strengthens and enlarges such a community, in preparation for post-project developments, e.g. for instance further pursuit of the PERSEUS treatment validation / trials, and further exploitation activities.

The Project Coordinator, together with partner QED, will share the strategy developed in this document with all the partners and the WP Leaders, inviting them to contribute ideas for the duration of the Project.

Envisioning an overall outreach plan at the beginning of the project ensures that we maximise the impact of dissemination, communication, and public engagement.

In order to make the Dissemination and Communication Plan effective, we have broken it down into a clear and specific set of constituent elements:

Goals: We set out at the beginning the objectives of our dissemination and communication efforts.

Target Audience and Message: We have identified and described the main target audiences of PERSEUS. For each of the target audiences, we have established the basic elements of the message to be disseminated.

Methods: We have described the media channels and the strategies through which the message of PERSEUS can be best delivered and established a set of clear and simple branding guidelines.

Success: We have listed the metrics to measure success and to monitor progress.

This document will be a living document, during the course of the project duration. This document and the corresponding dissemination activity tables (publications, journals, conference distributions, etc.) will be updated regularly; periodic tracking and tracing of the different activities will take place as well.

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ANNEX 1: ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

○ SHORT NAME OF PARTICIPANTS

Partner	Country	Short Name
Consiglio Nazionale Delle Ricerche	Italy (Coordinator)	CNR
Karolinska Institutet	Sweden	KI
Technion - Israel Institute Of Technology	Israel	TECHNION
Universidad De Vigo	Spain	UVIGO
Wigner Fizikai Kutatokozpont	Hungary	Wigner RCP
BeDimensional Spa	Italy	BeD
QED Film & Stage Productions Ltd.	United Kingdom	QED

○ LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Consortium Agreement	CA
Description of Action	DoA
Description of Work	DoW
European Commission	EC
Grant Agreement	GA
Kick-off Meeting	KoM
Project Management Board	PMB
Work Package	WP
Work Package Leader	WPL